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D6.3 Management and Optimization of City Resources Pilot v1

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2	STICHTING EGI	EGI	Netherlands		
3	NETCOMPANY-INTRASOFT	INTRA	Luxembourg		
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5	NOVOVILLE LIMITED	NOVO	United Kingdom		
6	UNPARALLEL INNOVATION LDA	UNP	Portugal		
7	VILABS (CY) LTD	VIL	Cyprus		
8	ARTHUR'S LEGAL BV	ALBV	Netherlands		
9	UNIVERSIDAD POLITECNICA DE MADRID	UPM	Spain		
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Abbreviations

AI	Artificial Intelligence
AI4PP	Artificial Intelligence for Public Policy
CSV	Comma Separated Values
EC	European Commission
EU	European Union
GA	Grant Agreement
H2020	Horizon 2020 Program of the European Commission
KPI	Key Policy Indicator
VO	Virtual Organisation
VPME	Virtualized Policy Management Environment
WP	Work Package

Executive summary

This deliverable describes the implementation of the AI4PP Pilot case on Management and Optimization of City Resources in Athens, Greece. Two policies have been defined, the first related to optimization of parking space allocation, and the second on maintenance incidents prediction for planning purposes.

Main steps in the implementation of this Pilot (Section 3) encompass: a) the systematization of data in relation to the policies with greater implementation potential, their cataloguing and curation; b) policy definition, testing and evaluation; and c) improvement of policies and continuous co-creation with the stakeholders' ecosystem. A user/stakeholder feedback collection plan (Section 4) and training plans (Section 5) have been described.

The document is the first version of a report on the activities within Task 6.2.

1 Introduction

1.1 The AI4PublicPolicy Project

AI4PublicPolicy is a joint effort of policy makers and Cloud/AI experts to unveil AI’s potential for automated, transparent and citizen-centric development of public policies. To this end, the project will deliver, validate, demonstrate and promote a novel Open Cloud platform (i.e., AI4PublicPolicy platform) for automated, scalable, transparent and citizen-centric policy management based on unique AI technologies. The AI4PublicPolicy platform will be an Open Virtualized Policy Management Environment (VPME) that will provide fully-fledged policy development/management functionalities based on AI technologies such as Machine Learning (ML), Deep Learning (DL), NLP and chatbots, while leveraging citizens’ participation and feedback. It will support the entire policy development lifecycle, based on technologies for the extraction, simulation, evaluation and optimization of interoperable and reusable public policies, with emphasis on citizen-centric policies development and optimization through the realization of citizen-oriented feedback loops. AI4PublicPolicy will complement public policy development functionalities with the ever-important process reengineering and organization transformation activities towards ensuring the effective transition from legacy policy development models to emerging AI-based policy making.

The AI4PublicPolicy VPME will be integrated with EOSC with a dual objective. First to facilitate access to the Cloud and HPC resources of EOSC/EGI that are required to enable the project’s AI tools, second to boost the sustainability and wider use of the project’s developments. AI4PublicPolicy’s business plan for sustaining, expanding and commercializing the AI tools and the VPME is based on the development of a community of interested and engaged stakeholders (i.e., public authorities and other policy makers) around the project’s platform.

Figure 1. AI4PublicPolicy methodological approach

1.2 Description of WP6

The WP6 is the pilot's work-package that will be devoted to deploying, operating, validating and evaluating the pilot systems with the active engagement of the public authorities of the consortium.

The main objectives are as follow:

- Undertake preparatory activities at the five (5) pilot sites towards their readiness for the pilot operations.
- Customise and deploy the AI4PublicPolicy outcomes in-line with the requirements and needs of the 5 pilot sites.
- Operate and validate the AI4PublicPolicy platform in different use cases and contexts in the 5 pilot sites.
- Evaluate the pilot systems from a technical and a business perspective.

1.3 Purpose and scope of the document

This deliverable will be devoted to the integration, deployment and operation of the project's pilot systems and policies. The work will involve tailoring and customization of the AI4PublicPolicy platform and tools to the needs of the pilot, including the implementation of pilot specific data models and features, as well as connectors to the data sources of the pilot.

The operation of the system will engage relevant stakeholders, including citizens, experts, and businesses. The task will continually improve the implementation and operation of the pilot systems and policies based on feedback from user studies and focus groups (as described in Task 2.6).

1.4 Structure of the document

This document is comprised of the following sections:

- **Section 1: Introduction** – This section presents an introduction to the project, the W6, the purpose and scope of the current document as well as its structure.
- **Section 2: Pilot policies** – contains all the details (policy name, user story, description, objective and KPIs) regarding the pilot policies that will be deployed for the pilot. In addition, the policy datasets are fully described. Finally, a demonstration of the definition of the policies and datasets with the usage of the Policy and Data Management Component is provided.
- **Section 3: New Policy Making Process Definition** – defines the new organisation processes that need to be in place in order to implement the new pilot policies. Moreover, it contains all details on how the various components of the VPME will be incorporated in the process and how the VPME will be used in the new policy making process; A screenshot of the single Virtual Organisation is provided.
- **Section 4: Feedback from Users/Stakeholders** – describes the methodologies that will be adopted to collect feedback from citizens and other relevant stakeholders; Screenshots from surveys created with the Policy Evaluation toolkit will be shown.
- **Section 5: Stakeholders involvement in VPME pilot use** – demonstrates the methodologies that will be followed to engage stakeholders in the internal implementation and usage of the VPME. Furthermore, pilots also describe the steps needed to be taken in order to train the stakeholders.

2 Pilot policies

2.1 Policy #1 – Optimized parking space allocation

This policy aims to provide city officials with a tool for optimal use of on-streets parking resources.

2.1.1 User stories

The User Stories that are related to this Policy are the following:

Table 1. List of User Stories explored in Policy #1

User Stories ID	As a «type of user», ... <i>Identify the customer job(s) to which this user story relates.</i>	... I want « <u>some goal</u> » ... <i>Describe the intended goal that the user expects to be fulfilled.</i>	... so that « <u>some reason</u> ». <i>Identify the reason(s) to which this user story relates.</i>
User Story #10	As a Citizen Driver	I want to have credible information on available / crowded parking spaces in the city	So, I can choose the right parking area and minimize the time looking for a parking space
User Story #11	As a Head of the Municipal Police	I want to know the areas with high/low parking space requests	So, I can allocate parking spaces between guests / residents more efficiently
User Story #12	As a Head of the Municipal Police	I want to know the duration of each parking space occupation per area	So, I can allocate parking spaces between guests / residents more efficiently
User Story #13	As a Head of the Municipal Police	I want to know the allocation of parking fines per day/time	So, I can allocate municipal officers patrol more efficiently
User Story #14	As a Policy Maker	I want to know the areas with high/low parking space requests per time of day	So, I can optimise fare prices and maximise Municipality revenue

2.1.2 Description

Identify on-street parking areas with high/low parking requests, so parking spaces between residents and guests can be allocated more efficiently to enable optimal use of space and high revenues for the city.

2.1.3 Objective

The available parking spaces in Athens are marked on the street and are distributed between residents of the city (special permit required) and guests (payment through parking app). Therefore, with this policy the Municipality of Athens would like to allocate more efficiently the available spaces between residents and guests, to make sure that there are no spaces left unused or missing at each season, while maximising the revenue from parking space tickets.

2.1.4 Key Policy Indicators (KPI)

The policy should identify the ratio between resident/guest parking spaces at a given season (e.g., summer, Christmas, etc.) that results to the following KPIs.

Table 2. KPI related to Policy #1

KPI	KPI Description
% Of parking spaces coverage	Percentage of available spaces allocated to city visitors that are occupied
Revenue from guest parking spaces	Percentage of increase in revenue from visitor parking spaces
Citizen satisfaction	Citizen satisfaction related to the availability and ease of finding a parking space
Time to park	Time reported by driver through the parking app that was needed to find a parking space

The KPIs may be updated / complimented in the future through users' and stakeholders' feedback.

The Policy has been defined in the VPME though the Policy management component:

Policies

Areas

POLICIES

Optimized parking space allocation More Information

Identify on-street parking areas with high/low parking requests, so parking spaces between residents and guests can be allocated more efficiently to enable optimal use of space and high revenues for the City.

Datasets:

Maintenance Incidents Prediction for Planning Purposes More Information

Predict maintenance incidents in the next months to plan material purchases and plan seasonal personnel.

Datasets:

Optimized parking space allocation

Objective: The available parking spaces in Athens are marked on the street and are distributed between residents of the city (special permit required) and guests (payment through parking app). Therefore, with this policy the Municipality of Athens would like to allocate more efficiently the available spaces between residents and guests, to make sure that there are no spaces left unused or missing at each season.

	KPIs
Name	Description
Percentage of parking spaces coverage	
Revenue from guest parking spaces	
Citizen satisfaction	

Figure 2. Definition of Policy #1 in the VPME

2.2 Policy #2 – Maintenance Incidents Prediction for Planning Purposes

This policy refers to the optimal allocation of maintenance resources (e.g., workers, vehicles, materials), as well as for scheduling of different maintenance activities in the city.

2.2.1 User stories

The User Stories that are related to this Policy are the following:

Table 3. List of User Stories explored in Policy #2

User Stories ID	As a «type of user», ... <i>Identify the customer job(s) to which this user story relates.</i>	... I want « <u>some goal</u> » ... <i>Describe the intended goal that the user expects to be fulfilled.</i>	... so that « <u>some reason</u> ». <i>Identify the reason(s) to which this user story relates.</i>
User Story #1	As a Head of Urban Planning Dept	I want to see a prediction/forecast of the completion time for each type of incident	so that I can provide a data driven feedback to citizens and the head of operations regarding the completion time
User Story #2	As a Head of Urban Planning Dept	I want to have a prediction of the incident's frequency per season of the year	in order to be able to plan the seasonal personnel according to forecasted needs

User Story #3	As a Head of Road Construction, Sewerage and Public Spaces Management Dept	i want to be able to set a route of incident fixes locations based on shortest path principle	so that i can optimize the personnel moving and vehicle costs and minimise the resolution time.
User Story #4	As a Head of Road Construction, Sewerage and Public Spaces Management Dept	I want to receive feedback from citizens about maintenance issues handling	So, I can improve the issue response time and quality
User Story #5	As a City Employee (in the Dept of Road Construction, Sewerage and Public Spaces Management/Urban Planning/Urban Green Spaces and Public Lighting	I want to have a prediction of incidents occurrence frequency	So, I can plan equipment / materials purchases in optimal prices (economies of scale, etc.)
User Story #6	As a City Employee (in the Dept of Road Construction, Sewerage and Public Spaces Management/Urban Planning/Urban Green Spaces and Public Lighting	I want to have an overview of the predicted maintenance needs in city assets (e.g. roads, lightning, pedestrian etc)	So, I can schedule activities more efficiently
User Story #7	As a Head of Dept of Road Construction, Sewerage and Public Spaces Management/Urban Planning/Urban Green Spaces and Public Lighting	I want to have an output report on estimated predictions for the timeline, human resources and cost of maintenance of the city	So, I can provide maintenance services proactively and increase QoS life in the city
User Story #8	As a citizen	I want to be informed of the outcome of my complaint / report	So, I can be sure my complaint has been addressed
User Story #9	As a City Worker	I want to have a schedule of the foreseen maintenance and other repairing issues	So, I can estimate and manage my weekly/monthly workload

2.2.2 Description

Predict maintenance incidents in the next months to plan material purchases and plan seasonal personnel.

2.2.3 Objective

Have a reliable forecast of maintenance incidents in the coming months, or per season, to plan more efficiently the purchase or consumables and to plan for seasonal personnel hiring or allocation.

2.2.4 Key Policy Indicators (KPI)

Table 4. KPI related to Policy #2.

KPI	KPI Description
Incident prediction accuracy	Percentage of accuracy on incident
Cost of consumables reduced	Percentage of procurement cost reduction
% Of incidents that did not have required consumables after 2 days	Percentage of delayed consumable procurement
How early can I know what consumables I will need with success rate 80%	Forecast on consumables to be purchased

The KPIs may be updated / complimented in the future through users' and stakeholders' feedback. The Policy has been defined in the VPME though the Policy management component:

Figure 3. Definition of Policy #2 in the VPME

2.3 Policy Datasets

In this section, the details for all the datasets relevant to the policy under evaluation, described in 2.1, are provided:

Table 5. Datasets associated to Policy #1

Name	Description	Source	Source type
------	-------------	--------	-------------

Parking transactions	Purchases/activations that the citizens or visitors execute for parking tickets	File	CSV, JSON
Wallet transactions	Transactions that the citizens or visitors execute with their digital wallet for parking services	File	CSV, JSON

Table 6. Datasets associated to Policy #2

Name	Description	Source	Source type
Incident management reports	All the incidents that are reported by citizens in the city of Athens and are sent to the Municipal authorities for resolution	File	CSV, JSON
Incident management reports activity	Activity history of incidents that are reported by citizens in the city of Athens and are sent to Municipal authorities for resolution,	File	CSV, JSON

The Datasets have been defined and uploaded in the VPME though the Dataset management component:

Dataset Definition

Register a new dataset

Area

Dataset Name Source Type Image format
 csv [v]

The new dataset name.
 Dataset description

Owner Language
 Greek [v]

Dataset owner.

Dataset fields definition Add field

DEFINE EACH FIELD OF THE DATASET

Field #1 ^				
Name	Description	Type	Default value	
<input type="text" value="Creation date"/>	<input type="text"/>	Datetime ▾	<input type="text"/>	X
Field #2 ^				
Name	Description	Type	Default value	
<input type="text" value="Type"/>	<input type="text"/>	String ▾	<input type="text"/>	X
Field #3 ^				
Name	Description	Type	Default value	
<input type="text" value="Service type"/>	<input type="text"/>	String ▾	<input type="text"/>	X
Field #4 ^				
Name	Description	Type	Default value	
<input type="text" value="Amount"/>	<input type="text"/>	String ▾	<input type="text"/>	X
Field #5 ^				
Name	Description	Type	Default value	
<input type="text" value="Success status"/>	<input type="text"/>	Double ▾	<input type="text"/>	X
Field #6 ^				
Name	Description	Type	Default value	
<input type="text" value="Start parking at"/>	<input type="text"/>	Datetime ▾	<input type="text"/>	X
Field #7 ^				
Name	Description	Type	Default value	
<input type="text" value="End parking at"/>	<input type="text"/>	Datetime ▾	<input type="text"/>	X

Figure 4. Dataset registration in the VPME

Datasets

Areas

DATASETS

Figure 5. Datasets defined in the VPME

3 New Policy Making Process Definition

The new organisation processes that need to be in place in order to implement the new pilot policies are presented in this section, including the various components of the VPME that will be incorporated in the new policy making process.

Data related to the policies are collected through a variety of sources and are inserted in the VPME as primary information to be analysed. The City Departments responsible for the policies in discussion, supported by DAEM, the City’s IT provider, define the policies and related KPIs in the VPME with the support of AI experts. The City Departments receive recommendations from the VPME and proceed to the update of existing policies by making policy recommendations to the City Council. Policy recommendations are then evaluated by Citizens through surveys before being implemented.

Figure 6. Schematic of the Policy #1 process based on VPME

The role of the AI expert is to create and train the AI models based on the policies defined and the data available and finetune them after the first run. Policy makers and other stakeholders view the outcomes of the policy analysis and the respective KPIs in the dashboards. New data is constantly fed into the platform, and further model finetuning takes place as necessary. The policies are evaluated both by stakeholders and citizens through feedback surveys developed through the VPME. The policy makers present the suggested policies to the City Council for further refinement or final approval.

Figure 7. Schematic of the Policy #2 process based on VPME

To define, extract, test and evaluate policies, the users must be registered in the EGI Community, through the EGI Check-in service, and ask to join the AI4PublicPolicy Virtual Organization (VO) specifying the role (Policy Maker or AI Expert) and the pilot group within VPME. More details on the onboarding phase could be found in deliverable D5.10 “Virtualized Policy Management Environment V1”. The group for Athens Pilot was created inside the VO and the list of current users can be seen in the following figure:

EGI User Community

Home > EGI User Community > My Population

EGI User Community People

Toggle All: Open Closed Sort By: ▲ Name Status Created Modified

Filter

Given Name	Identifier
Family Name	Status (select...)
Email	ai4publicpolicy-athens

CLEAR

a b c d e f g h i j k l m n o p q r s t u v w x y z

▶ Avatangelou Avatangelou (euprojects@daem.gr)	Policy Maker	Active	Edit
▶ Ioannis Christou (ichristou@netcompany-intrasoft.com)	AI Expert	Active	Edit
▶ Babis Ipeksidis (babis.ipeksidis@netcompany-intraso...)	AI Expert	Active	Edit
▶ Thanasis Papadakis (thanasis.papadakis@netcompany-intra...)	AI Expert	Active	Edit
▶ Tsironis Serafeim (serafeim.tsironis@netcompany-intras...)	AI Expert	Active	Edit

Figure 8. List of users of the Pilot group in the VO

4 Feedback from Users/Stakeholders

In this section, the methods that will be adopted to collect feedback from citizens and other relevant stakeholders are described.

4.1 Feedback Collection Plan and Methods

The Athens team is planning to mobilise all relevant stakeholders into the evaluation of policies, by using the following methods.

- Comprehensive citizen feedback surveys via AI4PublicPolicy App

Surveys to receive feedback from citizens can be developed through the AI4PublicPolicy App. This feedback can help evaluate and refine the policy and catch the public's opinion on relevant matters.

An example of survey to collect feedback from citizens has been created through the Policy Evaluation toolkit component in the VPME:

Figure 9. Preliminary feedback survey created in the VPME

- Social quick surveys on Twitter via AI4PublicPolicy App

To reach out to a broader audience, very concise questions can be launched to the public via Twitter and get point-in-time feedback.

- The Novoville app poll mechanism

The Novoville app enables policy makers to reach citizens and receive their feedback through the mobile application by creating announcements, polls, surveys, etc.

- Usability tests and exploratory interviews

Additional co-creation workshops will be organized, involving relevant stakeholders and policy makers, to test, evaluate, validate and receive feedback about the VPME and the policies. Workshops will be organised either in groups, or one-to-one, depending on the stakeholder involved and the desired level of detail in the discussion.

Additional feedback methods will be employed in the following months of the project.

5 Stakeholders involvement in VPME pilot use

5.1 Engagement plan and status

This section describes the methods to engage stakeholders in the internal implementation and usage of the VPME, including identification and steps to engage potential users of the VPME.

The project seeks to enhance the civic engagement to the policy development cycle and increase the transparency and trust in the policy-making processes. AI4PublicPolicy solutions are developed based on a co-creation approach that engages the local ecosystems in the policy development activities. Hence, the involvement of local stakeholders, including potential VPME users, AI experts, decision makers and higher management officers in public administrations, social groups and NGOs, is intrinsic to the VPME implementation, pilot usage and evaluation.

The engagement of stakeholders from the local ecosystems where pilot partners are positioned is parallel to the three phases of the project work plan.

- **Phase 1 (M1-M9):** Specification & Fine Tuning of the AI4PublicPolicy Concept
- **Phase 2 (M10-M24):** Initial Integration & Technical Validation
- **Phase 3 (M25-M36):** Technical & Business Validation

Within each Phase specific objectives for the engagement of stakeholders are set based on the project’s work plan and input; and dedicated activities and outputs are provided.

Phase 1 (M1-M9): Specification & Fine Tuning of the AI4PublicPolicy Concept

Objectives	Collect insights on the status of production processes, as well as the challenges and potentials of introducing AI systems. Review Use Cases and reference scenarios to conclude, update and extend User Stories	
Input	Preliminary Use Cases and User Stories	
Actors	Responsible(s)	Participants
	DAEM (ATH)	Public and local authorities Citizen groups and associations Researchers and academia experts Companies and entities of the city maintenance and parking management sector
Activities	2 Co-creation Workshops	
Outputs	Consolidated list of Use Cases and priority User Stories	

Phase 2 (M10-M24): Initial Integration & Technical Validation

Objectives	Develop the preliminary proof-of-concept (PoC) of the VPME prototype demonstrators Review and update Use Cases and User Stories Collect users’ feedback on the preliminary demonstrators regarding user experience features, usability, security ethics and overall concept Conduct preliminary business modelling exercise
-------------------	--

Input	Policy resources Data sets Use Cases and User Stories VPME prototype demonstrators	
Actors	Responsible(s)	Participants
	DAEM (ATH)	Policy makers Business and market experts Public and local authorities Citizen groups and associations Researchers and academia experts Companies and entities of the city maintenance and parking management sector
Activities	2 Co-creation Workshops	
Outputs	Assessment of the prototype demonstrators Updated list of User Stories	

Phase 3 (M25-M36): Technical & Business Validation

Objectives	Pilot test the integrated VPME solutions Collect users' feedback on the preliminary demonstrators regarding user experience features, usability, security ethics and overall concept & Benchmark with previous Phase input Validate Exploitation and sustainability pathways via the updated business modelling exercise	
Input	Improved Policy #1 resources Other Policies defined Use Cases and User Stories	
Actors	Responsible(s)	Participants
	DAEM (ATH)	Policy makers Business and market experts Public and local authorities Citizen groups and associations Researchers and academia experts Companies and entities of the city maintenance and parking management sector
Activities	2 Co-creation Workshops	
Outputs	Assessment of integrated VPME solutions Validated Business Models	

5.2 Training plan and status

The training needs of different stakeholders are described next. To this end, group and/or one-on-one dedicated sessions (as described in 4.1) will be carried on after the integrated VPME solutions become available.

Table 7. Training Plan and Status (DAEM)

Stakeholder type	Role	Training requirements
Public and local authorities	<p>End-users (policy makers), Data providers, Feedback providers, Business opportunities</p> <p>Authorities will help to shape up the AI4PP VPME functionalities and layouts, and the ambition of the tool based on the data availability.</p> <p>Municipality officers will refer to the VPME to inform their policy definition and decision-making rationale.</p>	<p>Training materials?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Policy resources - VPME walkthrough - Policy definition standalone exercise <p>Where?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - DAEM premises - Stakeholder premises <p>Trainer?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - DAEM - Relevant project partners
Researchers and academia experts	<p>Expertise, Data providers, Feedback providers, Project opportunities</p> <p>Building on the science that has been produced, state-of-the-art methods and innovative products and services, the VPME improvements will benefit greatly from work sessions with the local experts on AI, ML and big data monitoring and analytics.</p> <p>R&D projects in relation to the city’s policy development and implementation might also find use in the framework and components behind VPME.</p>	<p>Training materials?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Policy resources (focus on the AI model and text analysis used) - VPME walkthrough - Data Catalogue showcase - Research question exercise <p>Where?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - DAEM premises - Remotely <p>Trainer?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - DAEM - Relevant project partners
Citizen groups and associations	<p>Beneficiaries, Feedback providers, NGOs</p> <p>Citizens will provide input to fine-tuning the VPME, by voicing on to what level the decisions based on the tools are answering their needs.</p> <p>They do not require VPME training per se, but they must be well informed about what’s behind the tool and why they are needed.</p>	<p>Training materials?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Policy resources (focus on mapping and text analysis) - VPME summary - Surveying and polling exercises <p>Where?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - DAEM premises - Remotely <p>Trainer?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - DAEM

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